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Palpares lilii sp. n. – a new species of antlion from Namibia (Neuroptera: Myrmeleontidae)

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Abstract: *Palpares lilii* sp. n. is described from Namibia and compared to other species in the tribe Palparini, namely *Palpares cataractae* PÉRINGUEY, 1910, *P. ertli* (NAVÁS, 1912) and *Annularis aspoecki* MANSELL, 2004, which are all known from southern Africa.

Key words: Palparini, taxonomy, new species, Namibia, Africa.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Palpares* RAMBUR, 1842 is distributed in Africa, southern Asia, and southern Europe, and includes many of the largest and most decorative of the antlion species (MANSELL 2004). This genus (sensu RAMBUR) is not phylogenetically homogeneous, and several genera have already been separated (including *Annulares* MANSELL, 2004; *Crambomorphus* McLACHLAN, 1867; *Golafrus* NAVÁS, 1912; *Goniocerus* INSOM & CARFI, 1988; *Indopalpares* INSOM & CARFI, 1988; *Lachlathetes* NAVÁS, 1926; *Palparellus* NAVÁS, 1912; *Parapalpares* INSOM & CARFI, 1988 and *Pseudopalpares* INSOM & CARFI 1988). Most of the genera are of southern African origin (HEVIN *et al.* 2023) and have the greatest species diversity in southern Africa compared to other zoogeographic regions (STITZ 2012, BANKS 1913, HÖLZEL 1986, MANSELL 1992a, STANGE 2004, OSWALD 2024).

MANSELL (1992a) has already started the revision work and grouped the species into four divisions, some of which he transferred to other genera (MANSELL, 1996, 2004, 2018). During these revisional works covering southern Africa, MANSELL (1990, 1992a,b, 1996, 2004, 2018) has published the results of the tribe Palparini in six papers so far.

The genus *Palpares* includes species with very different morphology and distribution, therefore many researchers agree that the genus needs a complete revision (MICHEL *et al.* 2017, HEVIN *et al.* 2023), which should also be confirmed by further morphological studies of the larvae and molecular analysis.

Although the African fauna is poorly known, the majority of species in this genus and related genera were already described by the middle of the last century, perhaps due to their size, striking nature and their representation in museum collections. However, recently, morphologically

very similar new species have been separated (e.g. *Pamares* spp. MANSSELL, 1990, *Palpares longimaculatus* AKOUDJIN & MICHEL, 2011, *Pseudopalpares parvopunctatus* ÁBRAHÁM, 2023).

Palpares and related genera are found in all major museums and private collections. While identifying a private insect collection in Hungary, I found an unknown African *Palpares* species, which is described in this paper.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The habitus photos were taken by Canon EOS 6DM2 digital camera equipped with Canon macro lens 100 mm and a flashlight system (Godox MS 300). Later, the layers of photos were processed with stacking and Adobe Photoshop software.

According to traditional methods, the caudal part of the abdomen was removed, treated with a 10% KOH solution, and heated for 15 minutes. After cooling, it was rinsed in distilled water. For taking photos, the genitalia was placed in glycerine in a Petri dish. Finally, each genitalia was transferred into glycerine in a microvial for preservation.

TAXONOMY

Myrmeleontidae LATREILLE, 1802

Palparinae BANKS, 1911

Palparini BANKS, 1911

Palpares RAMBUR, 1842

Palpares lili sp. n.

<https://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/5890B6A9-26A1-42F9-B41A-1E384E12F43F>

(Figs. 1–2)

Holotype ♂ Namibia, Tirasberge Conservancy 1300m, 1 km SW of Ranch Koiimasis, 25°55,26'S 16°15,78'E 16.01.2015 leg. L. Jakab.

Type material is preserved in the Ludvig-collection, Hungary.

Diagnosis. The new species is of medium size among the species of *Palpares* RAMBUR, 1842, the forewing length ca. 50 mm. A striking feature of the new species is the black head and thorax, with dense white hairs on the thorax. There are a few species in the Palparini tribe that have both wing tips subacute and concave below the tip (e.g. *Lachlathetes moestus* (HAGEN, 1853). The wing pattern is close to *Palpares cataractae* PÉRINGUEY, 1910, but the wing tip of this species is rounded, and the margin below the tip is not concave. The frons of *P. cataractae* is yellow, while that of the new species is black. The new sp. also resembles *P. ertli* (NAVÁS, 1912), which has well-developed cross bands on its wings, but *P. ertli* also has a rounded wing tip. Thus, it can be easily distinguished from these species in the southern Africa. Some features of the new species, black frons and dense white hairs on thorax, are also similar to the endemic *Annularis aspoECKi* MANSSELL, 2004. However, the abdomen of new sp. is shorter than that of *A. aspoECKi* and the tip of the wing shape is also rounded and the pattern on the hindwing is different.

Description.

Measurements. Male: Body length: 56 mm; forewing length: 49 mm, width 12 mm; hindwing: length 46 mm, width 12 mm.

Head: Vertex dark brown to black with short sparse and white setae. Epicranial suture remarkably deep. Frons shining black with scattered sparse and white setae. Gena yellowish next to frons and dark brown next to eyes. Eye slightly larger than hemispherical, as wide as width of frons. Upper part of clypeus shiny black with sparse white hairs, lower part yellow and aetose. Labrum predominantly shiny black. Mandibles brown to black with black apex. Maxillary and labial palps shiny black, brownish-yellow at joints. Labial palps short, clavate, apex truncate, palpimacula with slit-shaped opening. Scape black covered with longer black and shorter white setae, pedicel black with yellow distal ring. Antenna clavate, flagellar segments reddish-brown covered with short black setae, club yellowish-brown.

Thorax: Pronotum (Fig. 2) shorter than wide, subrumboid-shaped. Prescutum yellow with narrow brown medial band. Long stiff black and white hairs on anterior margin. Oblique inflection moderately deep. Rest of pronotum brown to black with yellowish-brown posterior margin covered with long black and white hairs. Mesonotum and metanotum predominantly brown with indistinct yellow marks covered with very dense soft white hairs. Sides brown to black with dense soft white hairs.

Wings: Forewing membrane transparent with large dark brown spots and many scattered dots. C yellow, covered with dense dark brown setae. Sc and R brown basally, then yellow and alternating dark brown at cross-veins distally. Veins also brown in brown spot areas. Pterostigma distinct white. Tip subacute, below clearly visible falcate in apical margin. Apical band inconspicuously divided into two parts. Prestigmal and medial bands marked by two larger separate spots. Many dots scattered more or less evenly over entire wing plate and costal field.

Hindwing membrane transparent; pterostigma distinct white. Tip of hindwing subacute and falcated. Apical band clearly divided with wide transparent strip into two brown marks. Prestigmal band extends from costal margin to hind margin with a medial projection towards the medial band. Medial band extends from middle of wing to hind margin, strongly curved. Basal band medium-sized, slightly oval-shaped.

Legs: Short, strong, dark brown to black. Coxae covered with dense white hairs. Femora longer than tibiae covered with short dense white setae and stiff black bristles ventrally. Tarsal segments 1-4 subequal, yellow; segment 5 slightly longer than segments 1-4 combined. Each segment with stiff shiny black setae. Tibial spurs reddish brown and as long as tarsal segments 1-2 combined. Claws shining reddish brown one and a half times longer than tibial spurs.

Abdomen: slightly longer than hindwing in resting position, Tergite 1 brown with long white hairs. Tergites 2-4 yellow, and tergal segments 5-8 predominantly brown with narrow longitudinal yellow midline in dorsal view. Tergal segments covered with short black setae. Sternites brown covered with white setae.

Terminalia and genitalia: Anterior part of ectoproct brown, caudal part yellow. Caudo-ventral lobe curved at right angles brown basally, yellow distally (Fig. 1E), covered with black hairs and short spine-like setae on inner surface, only single rigid basal spine (Fig. 1E). Sternite 8 tongue-shaped, brown anteriorly, yellow distally, with long curved black hairs arranged in a row (Fig. 2B). Genitalia as in Fig. 2C and D in lateral and ventral view.

Female: Unknown.

Etymology: The new species is named after the collection owner's daughter (Lili), at his request. The given name Lili (Lily) comes from the Latin word *lilium*.

Habitat: The collection site for the new species is part of the Tiras Conservancy (Tirasberge Naturpark), where the eroded granite cliffs of the Tiras Mountains rise from the red sandy

Fig. 1. Holotype of *Palpares lilii* sp. n., A – habitus in dorsal view, scale bar: 10 mm; B – head and labial palp in frontal view; C – vertex and notum in dorsal view; D – thorax and leg in lateral view; E – male terminalia in lateral view, in different scales.

Fig. 2. Terminalia and genitalia of *Palpares lilii* sp. n., **A** – male terminalia in lateral view, **B** – the same in ventral view; **C** – gonocoxites gx9 + 11 (gonarcus and parameres complex) in lateral view; **D** – the same in ventral view, in different scales. Abbreviations: **bs** – basal spine, **gs** – gonatal setae.

plains of the Namibian desert. There are numerous grass species adapted to the dry desert climate and many succulents in the mountains. The ephemeral watercourses, which only hold water during heavy rains, are locally dotted with bushes and trees.

Distribution: Known only in Namibia.

DISCUSSION

There are 36 valid *Palpares* species known from the African continent (STANGE 2004, OSWALD 2024), of which 13 species occur only in the Northern Hemisphere. The diversification of *Palpares* and related genera is highest in southern Africa (MANSELL 2004). In Namibia, 24 species, eight genera (*Annulares* 2, *Crambromorphus* 4, *Golafrus* 1, *Palparellus* 4, *Palpares* 6, *Pamares* 3, *Pseudopalpares* 3, *Tomatares* 1) have been documented in the tribe of Palparini (OSWALD 2024). Of these, six species can be recorded in the genus *Palpares* based on the NAMIBIA BIODIVERSITY DATABASE (2024).

The new species is placed within the genus *Palpares*, however, as a revision of the genus is currently in progress, it is possible this and genetic tests may result in a new combination. In the future, it will be worth revising the newly described species at the genus level based on larval morphology and molecular methods. The new species differs from the other species of *Palpares* and species of the related genera that are known either from Namibia or neighboring countries' fauna.

The new species can be easily recognized and distinguished based on the following features: medium size, subacute and falcate wing tips, brown markings of the hind wing, characteristic black head (vertex and frons), pronotum pattern, dense hairs on meso and metathorax, and genital organs.

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Database

Namibia Biodiversity Database. <https://www.biodiversity.org.na/> [Accessed 12 June 2024].

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